

Exploring Deep Reinforcement Learning for MAV Trajectory Tracking and Collision Avoidance

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Abstract— In this extended abstract, propose a novel Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) approach that enables Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) to autonomously track reference trajectories while effectively avoiding collisions using only depth maps and the robot’s current pose. The proposed method imposes no constraints on the drone’s mobility, allowing free navigation in three-dimensional space and does not require detailed information about the environmental characteristics and the shape and distribution of obstacles. Through comprehensive evaluations in photo-realistic simulated environments, we demonstrate the effectiveness and generalization capabilities of our strategy compared to state-of-the-art baselines.

Index Terms—trajectory tracking, collision avoidance, MAV, deep reinforcement learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) have garnered significant attention in the robotics research community [1], [2]. Owing to their compact size and agile flight capabilities, MAVs provide effective solutions across a broad spectrum of applications, including surveillance, exploration, scene reconstruction, and environmental monitoring.

In many of these applications, the trajectories to be followed, either user-defined or generated by high-level planners, are computed based on simplified environmental models that overlook the actual scene structure and the presence of obstacles. A key requirement for safe MAV operation is to track the reference trajectory as precisely as possible while avoiding collisions with unforeseen obstacles. This necessitates that the MAV navigation system possesses both trajectory tracking and collision avoidance capabilities.

In this work, we propose a novel approach that jointly addresses the trajectory tracking and collision avoidance problems, under the hypothesis that the only sensor we can access to sense the operating environment is a front-looking depth camera. Although separate solutions for the trajectory tracking and vision-based collision avoidance problems have been extensively studied, integrating both into a unified framework poses significant challenges due to the potentially conflicting

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Fig. 1: Overview of our approach. Our solution tracks a reference position trajectory while avoiding collisions by processing depth maps and pose data.

objectives. Specifically, our aim is to ensure that the MAV follows a reference trajectory as accurately as possible, which may be infeasible due to unconsidered obstacles during planning, while simultaneously avoiding collisions. A graphical representation of the considered problem is provided in Figure 1.

To address the task, we leverage the Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework to train a model that processes the depth maps acquired by the vision sensor and the current MAV pose to generate velocity commands. These commands are applied to the drone to track the reference trajectory while avoiding collisions.

II. METHODOLOGY

We address the task of enabling a Micro Aerial Vehicle (MAV) to track a reference trajectory while avoiding collisions, aiming to minimize deviation from the desired path. The MAV has access only to depth maps from a front-facing RGB-D camera and its own position, which can be obtained via GPS or visual odometry [3]. To compute control actions, we employ a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) approach, training the agent in a simulated environment to safely generate sequences of observations, actions, and rewards. Although our method is model-free and does not require knowledge of the MAV dynamics during deployment, we utilize a rigid-body MAV dynamic model during simulation to generate realistic training data [4].

In our RL formulation, at each time step, the agent observes sequences of past MAV positions, future reference positions,

Fig. 2: Qualitative evaluation of the performance of the proposed method and the baselines in three different experimental scenarios. For each method we display the top and side views of the performed trajectory (in blue). The reference trajectory is depicted in red.

and depth maps. The action is a desired velocity command $\mathbf{v}_d(t_i)$, constrained within acceptable limits. This command is used to compute the control input through a pipeline of proportional controllers, translating desired velocities into jerk commands. The reward function is designed to encourage the MAV to minimize the position error while avoiding collisions, with penalties applied in case of collisions. To enhance robustness and generalization, we introduce noise into observations and control inputs, simulating real-world sensor inaccuracies and model mismatches.

We employ an asymmetric actor-critic framework, where the actor network receives noisy observations and outputs actions, while the critic network has access to privileged information during training, such as ground-truth positions and noiseless depth maps. Training is performed using the Soft Actor-Critic algorithm [5], suitable for continuous control tasks. To improve learning efficiency, we utilize curriculum learning [6]: we first train the agent on trajectory tracking without obstacles. Once satisfactory performance is achieved, we introduce obstacles into the environment.

III. EXPERIMENTS

We conducted simulated experiments to evaluate our DRL-based approach. The performance was measured using three metrics:

- **Success Rate (SR):** The percentage of trials where the MAV avoided collisions and maintained a tracking error inferior to a threshold of 10 meters.
- **Average Position Error (APE):** The mean tracking error over time.
- **Average Control Effort (ACE):** The mean magnitude of control inputs over time.

We compared our method against three baselines:

- 1) **APF-TFCA:** An adaptation of the vision-based Artificial Potential Fields method from [7], which computes velocity commands based on obstacle proximity and reference tracking.

- 2) **SAC-TO:** A DRL-based approach from [8] that uses RGB images to compute jerk control signals for tracking straight-line trajectories while avoiding obstacles.
- 3) **IL-TFCA:** An adaptation of the Imitation Learning approach from [9], modified to handle variable-speed reference trajectories and provide jerk control commands.

In our experiments, we tested our method and baselines across five different environments, including the training environment and four additional photorealistic outdoor scenarios: Baseball, Soccer, Playground, and Tennis. We evaluated performance at forward speeds ranging from 2.0 to 6.0 m/s.

Our method consistently outperformed the baselines, achieving higher success rates and lower average position errors, even in environments significantly different from the training setting. The results demonstrate that our approach generalizes well to new environments and is robust to varying reference speeds. Some qualitative views of the conducted simulated experiments are provided in Figure 2.

IV. CONCLUSION

We presented a novel Deep Reinforcement Learning approach that enables a Micro Aerial Vehicle to simultaneously track a reference trajectory and avoid collisions using only position measurements and depth maps. Extensive experiments in photo-realistic simulated environments demonstrate the effectiveness of the method, highlighting its generalization capabilities and robustness against sensing noise and model mismatches. Compared to state-of-the-art baselines, our approach consistently achieves superior overall performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Shraim, A. Awada, and R. Youness, “A survey on quadrotors: Configurations, modeling and identification, control, collision avoidance, fault diagnosis and tolerant control,” *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, vol. 33, no. 7, pp. 14–33, 2018.
- [2] T. Elmokadem and A. V. Savkin, “Towards fully autonomous uavs: A survey,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 18, 2021.
- [3] J. Engel, V. Koltun, and D. Cremers, “Direct sparse odometry,” *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 611–625, 2017.
- [4] M. W. Mueller, M. Hehn, and R. D’Andrea, “A computationally efficient motion primitive for quadcopter trajectory generation,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 1294–1310, 2015.
- [5] T. Haarnoja, A. Zhou, P. Abbeel, and S. Levine, “Soft actor-critic: Off-policy maximum entropy deep reinforcement learning with a stochastic actor,” in *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2018, pp. 1861–1870.
- [6] S. Narvekar, B. Peng, M. Leonetti, J. Sinapov, M. E. Taylor, and P. Stone, “Curriculum learning for reinforcement learning domains: A framework and survey,” *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2003.04960, 2020.
- [7] R. Brilli, M. Pozzi, F. Giorgetti, M. L. Fravolini, P. Valigi, D. Prattichizzo, and G. Costante, “Monocular reactive collision avoidance based on force fields for enhancing the teleoperation of mavs,” in *2021 20th International Conference on Advanced Robotics (ICAR)*, 2021, pp. 91–98.
- [8] R. Brilli, M. Legittimo, F. Crocetti, M. Leomanni, M. L. Fravolini, and G. Costante, “Monocular reactive collision avoidance for mav teleoperation with deep reinforcement learning,” in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2023, pp. 12535–12541.
- [9] A. Loquercio, E. Kaufmann, R. Ranftl, M. Müller, V. Koltun, and D. Scaramuzza, “Learning high-speed flight in the wild,” in *Science Robotics*, October 2021.